

Fuzzy rules with quantifiers as weights

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we explore the use of General Unary Hypotheses Automaton quantifiers and provide representations for their specific subclasses. Furthermore, we focus explicitly on implicational quantifiers for analyzing specific relational dependencies. We discuss their suitability in fuzzy modeling and demonstrate their integration with appropriate fuzzy rules to create a new class of weighted fuzzy rules. This study contributes to the advancement of fuzzy modeling and offers a framework for further research and practical applications.

1. Introduction

The advent of weighted fuzzy rules marks a significant advancement in fuzzy systems, enhancing both the precision and adaptability of (rough) fuzzy inference systems [1–3]. Recent developments have shown that integrating weighted factors into fuzzy rules allows for nuanced control over the rule's influence, effectively tailoring the system's response to varying degrees of certainty and importance assigned to each rule. This is particularly beneficial in areas such as pattern recognition, where weighted fuzzy rules facilitate more granular and dynamic decision-making processes.

Moreover, the application of weighted fuzzy rules in complex datasets has led to breakthroughs in data mining. By assigning different weights to individual rules, these advanced models can delineate more accurate decision boundaries. This is especially advantageous when dealing with datasets that exhibit overlapping or ambiguous feature distributions, enabling a more discerning classification of data points that might otherwise be challenging to categorize using conventional methods.

Various methodologies exist to model the relationships between input and output domains [4], which are particularly useful in deriving insights from databases or validating hypotheses concerning patterns observed within such databases [5–10]. These hypotheses are often articulated through a logical calculus framework, where database entries serve as fundamental observations that either corroborate or refute these hypotheses. In the context of databases with fuzzy attributes, patterns can be scrutinized using a four-fold table. This table accumulates data on the quantity of objects fulfilling the conditions set by all combinations of an antecedent “A”, a consequent “B”, “not A”, and “not B”, embodying their vague characteristics. This mechanism is crucial in the operations of both fuzzy association rules and the fuzzy General Unary Hypotheses Automaton (GUHA), as documented in sources such as Agrawal et al. [11], Nanavati et al. [12], Lee et al. [13], Hájek [14], and others [15–17]¹. Recent years have witnessed renewed interest in GUHA, spanning both theoretical developments and practical applications in fields such as epidemiology, online

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¹ It should be noted that fuzzy association rule mining constitutes a segment of the broader GUHA method.

retail, and driver behavior [8,18,19]. Modern implementations have also advanced beyond traditional systems like LISp-Miner [20] and EasyMiner [21] to contemporary frameworks such as *CleverMiner* [22,23], *nuggets* [10], and the *action* package [24,25].

Generated hypotheses may be represented by a collection of singular fuzzy rules, as explored by Holeňa [26] and Rauch [27]. Such tests are conducted using carefully selected quantifiers, extensively discussed by Ivánek and others [28,29]. Typically, these investigations employ bivalent quantifiers within the framework of the GUHA quantifier to generate fuzzy rules. While existing fuzzy rule mining methods and GUHA-based quantifier frameworks provide tools for reasoning with uncertainty, they often rely on bivalent or fixed-form quantifiers and lack flexibility in capturing gradual dependencies in functional relationships-particularly in datasets with overlapping or ambiguous characteristics.

In this paper, we build upon these foundations and contribute to the area of weighted fuzzy rules in several key ways.

- First, we focus on GUHA quantifiers represented by functions that take values in the range $[0, 1]$, capturing the gradual tightness of association between combinations of unary predicates. We introduce a new class of simple quantifiers, presented in Section 3, which can be viewed as a specialized subset of implicational quantifiers. These offer a more targeted and interpretable mechanism for assessing fuzzy dependencies. Furthermore, we propose a novel construction of double implicational and equivalence quantifiers, which fundamentally differs from the one introduced in [30], enabling a richer expression of logical relationships within fuzzy datasets.
- Next, we propose a new model that integrates GUHA-style implicational quantifiers with a novel formulation of weighted fuzzy rules. These quantifiers are particularly suitable for analyzing dependencies of the form “If antecedent, then consequent” and have been recognized in earlier works by Hájek [31] and Turunen [32]. Our contribution lies in the design of a hybrid framework in which tailored implicational quantifiers are embedded into weighted fuzzy rules, forming a new category of interpretable and data-sensitive fuzzy rules.
- In particular, we develop and apply this framework to model fuzzy functional dependencies, as detailed in Section 4. This extension enables the representation of relationships whose functional behavior is expressed in a fuzzy manner, thereby providing a more suitable formulation for scenarios where classical deterministic models may fail. Algorithm 1 constructs and evaluates implicational fuzzy rules for given antecedent-consequent pairs using specialized GUHA quantifiers. We present it as a representative algorithmic solution to the stated problem, accompanied by a rigorous analysis of its time complexity, while acknowledging that it constitutes only one of several possible approaches. Here, our direction diverges from the standard GUHA mining procedure in that the rules are explicitly defined, and the GUHA quantifiers serve merely as gradual modifiers. Example 11 illustrates that the proposed approach notably enhances explainability while remaining competitive in terms of predictive granularity when applied to real-world data with ambiguous or overlapping feature structures.
- Furthermore, we extend the framework to classification problems, focusing on the use of association rule mining (a special case of the GUHA procedure ASSOC) in combination with implicational models and specialized GUHA quantifiers. In Section 4.2, we formalize this modeling strategy, present an algorithmic procedure (see Algorithm 2) for rule mining, filtering, and inference, and analyze its computational complexity. This framework is then applied to a detailed case study in Example 12, where we demonstrate its applicability to crisp classification tasks using real-world data and compare it against traditional association rules-based classifiers.

Recent developments in *CleverMiner* [33,34] have introduced parameter-free modes that automatically select the number of extracted GUHA rules rather than specifying explicit quantifier thresholds. Additionally, they have expanded toward interpretable procedures that align with current trends in Explainable AI (XAI) [23]. While these advances emphasize automation and the transparent presentation of mined results, our approach takes a distinctly different direction: we formulate a fuzzy, model-based framework that explicitly defines implicational quantifiers and embeds them into weighted fuzzy rules to capture graded dependencies. Several conceptual ideas-such as rule aggregation or the treatment of quantifiers as interpretability modulators-could, however, be mutually reusable between both approaches.

The implementation of the proposed implicational models with GUHA quantifiers is publicly available in a GitHub repository², which contains the complete source code and examples related to Algorithm 1. Additionally, we provide the implementation of the classification procedure in a dedicated GitLab repository³. The procedure combines association rule mining, implemented with the *1f1* and *nuggets* packages [9,10], with implicational modeling as described in Algorithm 2. The repositories include scripts, data, and instructions for reproducing the experimental results.

2. Prerequisites

Definition 1. A *fuzzy conjunction* is a binary operation $\star : [0, 1]^2 \rightarrow [0, 1]$ that is commutative, associative, and for which the following conditions hold:

- *Annihilator*: $x \star 0 = 0$, for all $x \in [0, 1]$.
- *Unit*: $x \star 1 = x$, for all $x \in [0, 1]$.
- *Isotonicity*: for all $x, x', y, y' \in [0, 1]$: $x \leq x', y \leq y'$ implies $x \star y \leq x' \star y'$.

² https://github.com/martinadankova/implicative_models_with_quantifiers

³ <https://gitlab.com/Martina1976/assoc-rules-mining-and-modeling>

Note that the above definition of a fuzzy conjunction is, in fact, the definition of a t-norm; however, in the context of the subsequent discussion, we prefer to refer to it as a fuzzy conjunction. Moreover, the annihilator property follows from the subsequent axioms, but we choose to keep it in the definition.

Definition 2. A *fuzzy negation* is a unary operation $\neg: [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ satisfying the following.

- *Boundary conditions:* $\neg 0 = 1, \neg 1 = 0$.

We say that \neg is *involution* negation if $\neg\neg x = x$ for all $x \in [0, 1]$.

Convention 1. Let \star be a t-norm and \neg be an involutive negation. Then the *derived t-conorm* $\underline{\vee}^{****}$ is given by

$$x \underline{\vee} y = \neg(\neg x \star \neg y) \tag{1}$$

for all $x, y \in [0, 1]$.

Example 1. The well-known parametric families of involutive negations are Yager and Sugeno negations, which are given by

$$\neg_Y^c(x) = (1 - x^c)^{\frac{1}{c}}, \quad c \in]0, \infty], \tag{2}$$

$$\neg_{Su}^c(x) = \frac{1 - x}{1 + cx}, \quad c \in]-1, \infty]. \tag{3}$$

These negations can be constructed using continuous and strictly increasing generators $g: [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ with $g(0) = 0, g(1) = 1$ as follows:

$$\neg_g(x) = g^{-1}(1 - g(x)). \tag{4}$$

The generators of Yager and Sugeno negations are $g_Y^c(x) = x^c, c \in]0, \infty]$ and $g_{Su}^c(x) = \frac{\ln(1+cx)}{\ln(1+c)}, c \in]-1, \infty]$, respectively.

Definition 3. *Fuzzy implication* is a binary operation $\rightarrow: [0, 1]^2 \rightarrow [0, 1]$, for which the following conditions hold:

- *Boundary conditions:* $0 \rightarrow 0 = 1 \rightarrow 1 = 1, 1 \rightarrow 0 = 0$.
- *Monotony:* for all $x, x', y, y' \in [0, 1]$: $x \geq x', y \leq y'$ implies $x \rightarrow y \leq x' \rightarrow y'$.

We say that \rightarrow is *derived fuzzy implication* if for a t-conorm $\underline{\vee}$ and a fuzzy negation \neg , it is given by

$$x \rightarrow y = \neg x \underline{\vee} y, \tag{5}$$

for all $x, y \in [0, 1]$.

We say that \rightarrow is *residuated fuzzy implication* if it forms a residuated pair with a fuzzy conjunction \star , i.e.,

$$x \star y \leq z \text{ iff } x \leq y \rightarrow z, \text{ for all } x, y, z \in [0, 1].$$

Throughout this work, we often omit the word *fuzzy*, as its meaning is clear from the context. This allows us to ensure a concise and readable exposition without sacrificing clarity.

3. Fuzzy four-fold table quantifiers

In the sequel, we will use the following symbols:

- \star fuzzy conjunction,
 - \rightarrow fuzzy implication,
 - \neg fuzzy negation,
 - \wedge minimum,
 - \vee maximum.
- (6)

Moreover, let $\overline{\mathbb{R}} = \mathbb{R} \cup \{-\infty, +\infty\}$ denote the extended reals. Define the extended non-negative real half-line as

$$\overline{\mathbb{R}}_0^+ = \{x \in \overline{\mathbb{R}} \mid 0 \leq x \leq +\infty\}.$$

For simplicity of exposition, consider the following *data matrix*

$$D = \{(x_i, f(x_i))\}_{i \in I},$$

where $x_i \in X, f(x_i) \in Y, I = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}, X, Y \neq \emptyset$ and $f: X \rightarrow Y$. This D can be visualized as follows:

$$D = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & y_1 = f(x_1) \\ x_2 & y_2 = f(x_2) \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ x_n & y_n = f(x_n) \end{bmatrix}. \tag{7}$$

Definition 4 (4ft-table). Let A, B be fuzzy sets on $X, Y \neq \emptyset$, respectively, and D be a data matrix. We define a four-fold table for A, B w.r.t. D as a matrix 2×2

$$4ft(A, B) = \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix}, \tag{8}$$

where

$$a = \sum_{i \in I} (A(x_i) \star B(y_i)), \tag{9}$$

$$b = \sum_{i \in I} (A(x_i) \star \neg B(y_i)), \tag{10}$$

$$c = \sum_{i \in I} (\neg A(x_i) \star B(y_i)), \tag{11}$$

$$d = \sum_{i \in I} (\neg A(x_i) \star \neg B(y_i)). \tag{12}$$

The values of the matrix $4ft(A, B)$ are connected to the fuzzy cardinalities of the data matrix within the corresponding fuzzy Cartesian product. For example, the value a is calculated as the fuzzy cardinality of D over the fuzzy intersection of A and B . Define the following fuzzy set theoretical notions:

$$\bar{A}(x) = \neg A(x), \tag{13}$$

$$|A| = \sum_{x \in X} A(x), \tag{14}$$

$$(A \cap B)(x) = A(x) \star B(x), \tag{15}$$

$$(A \cup B)(x) = A(x) \vee B(x), \tag{16}$$

$$(A \times B)(x, y) = A(x) \star B(y), \tag{17}$$

$$A \subseteq B \text{ if } A(x) \leq B(x) \text{ for all } x \in X, \tag{18}$$

then

$$a = |(A \times B) \cap D|, \quad b = |(A \times \bar{B}) \cap D|, \tag{19}$$

$$c = |(\bar{A} \times B) \cap D|, \quad d = |(\bar{A} \times \bar{B}) \cap D|. \tag{20}$$

In the sequel, it will be more efficient to handle the relativized values of 4ft-table, for which we will use the same symbols whenever it is clear from the context:

$$a_R = P(A \cap B) = a/n, \tag{21}$$

$$b_R = P(A \cap \bar{B}) = b/n, \tag{22}$$

$$c_R = P(\bar{A} \cap B) = c/n, \tag{23}$$

$$d_R = P(\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}) = d/n. \tag{24}$$

Therefore, instead of cardinalities, we will work with probabilities.

The following definition is taken from [30].

Definition 5 (4ft-quantifier). A fuzzy four-fold table quantifier Q , or briefly, 4ft-quantifier Q , is a map defined on the set of all fuzzy four-fold tables, i.e., $Q: (\overline{\mathbb{R}}_0^+)^4 \rightarrow [0, 1], (a, b, c, d) \mapsto e$.

For a particular four-fold table $4ft(A, B)$ of the form (8), we often write $Q(A, B)$ instead of $Q(a, b, c, d)$.

Special subclasses of 4ft-quantifiers were designed to provide a versatile tool to express and quantify various degrees of dependency and causality between (fuzzy) sets based on observations from the data matrix; see [29].

Convention 2. To simplify the notation, we write fuzzy quantifiers as maps of fewer variables when they do not depend on all variables.

Definition 6. Let Q be a fuzzy four-fold table quantifier.

- We say that Q is a *simple quantifier* if it is monotone, i.e.,

$$\text{if } a \leq a' \text{ then } Q(a) \leq Q(a'), \tag{25}$$

is valid for all $a, a' \in \mathbb{R}_0^+$.

- We say that Q is an *implicational quantifier* if it is join monotone, i.e.,

$$\text{if } a \leq a' \text{ and } b' \leq b, \text{ then } Q(a, b) \leq Q(a', b'), \tag{26}$$

is valid for all $a, b, a', b' \in \mathbb{R}_0^+$.

Fig. 1. Functions from Example 2.

- We say that Q is a *double implicational quantifier* if it satisfies the following property:

$$\text{if } a \leq d' \text{ and } b' \leq b \text{ and } c' \leq c, \text{ then } Q(a, b, c) \leq Q(a', b', c'), \tag{27}$$

for all $a, b, c, a', b', c' \in \mathbb{R}_0^+$.

- We say that Q is an *equivalence quantifier* if it satisfies the following property:

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{if } a \leq d' \text{ and } b' \leq b \text{ and } c' \leq c \text{ and } d \leq d', \\ &\text{then } Q(a, b, c, d) \leq Q(a', b', c', d'), \end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

for all $a, b, c, d, a', b', c', d' \in \mathbb{R}_0^+$.

Example 2. Let $x, y, z, t \in \overline{\mathbb{R}}_0^+$, $a, b, c, d \in \overline{\mathbb{R}}_0^+$, $f(x) = \frac{x}{x+1}$, $g(x) = \frac{1}{x+1}$ (see Fig. 1), and \star be an arbitrary t-norm. Then by the monotonicity of both f, g and the conjunction \star , the following functions

$$\begin{aligned} Q(a) &= f(ax), \\ Q(a, b) &= f(ax) \star g(by), \\ Q(a, b, c, d) &= f(ax) \star g(by) \star g(cz) \star f(dt) \end{aligned}$$

are simple, implicational, and double implicational quantifiers, respectively.

3.1. Simple and implicational quantifiers

The exposition in this section begins with the well-investigated class of implicational quantifiers, reflecting their established historical study. Subsequently, the focus shifts to the newly introduced class of simple quantifiers, which can be regarded as a special case of implicational quantifiers.

3.1.1. Implicational quantifiers

It has been established [29] that there is a direct relationship between implicational quantifiers and fuzzy implications, whereby each fuzzy implication can be used to construct a corresponding implicational quantifier. The study presented two distinct methodologies for formulating implicational quantifiers based on fuzzy implications, which we recall below.

Proposition 1. (Theorems 1 and 2 in [29]). Let a, b be the values of a four-fold table, $p, r \in (0, 1)$ be weights and \rightarrow be a fuzzy implication. Then the following functions

$$Q_{p,r}(a, b) = (p^{a+1}) \rightarrow (r^{b+1}), \tag{29}$$

$$Q(a, b) = \left(\frac{b}{a+b} \right) \rightarrow \left(\frac{a}{a+b} \right), \tag{30}$$

are implicational quantifiers.

For quantifiers obtained by these constructions, we have the following properties:

- Consider a residuated implication \rightarrow . Then $Q_{p,r}(a, b) = 1$, for if $a \geq \frac{\ln r}{\ln p} \cdot (b + 1) - 1$.
- Consider $p = r$. Then $Q_{p,r}(a, b) = 1$, whenever $a = b$.
- $Q(a, b) = 1$, for if $b = 0$.
- Consider a residuated implication \rightarrow . Then $Q(a, b) = 1$ if and only if $a \geq b$ or equivalently $\frac{a}{a+b} \geq 0.5$.

Due to the last property, it is more suitable to use non-residuated implications in (30), such as the Kleene-Dienes or Reichenbach implication.

By observing the above special constructions of the implicational quantifier, we found that there is a large class of implicational quantifiers that are based on non-increasing mappings. It was also independently shown in [30] (see Theorem 29 and 30) that, under some constraints, fuzzy implications and implicational quantifiers are dual notions.

Theorem 1. Let $g, h : \overline{\mathbb{R}}_0^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$.

- If g, h are non-increasing, then

$$Q_{g,h}(a, b) = g(a) \rightarrow h(b) \tag{31}$$

is an implicational quantifier.

- If g, h are non-decreasing, then

$$Q_{g,h}(a, b) = g(b) \rightarrow h(a) \tag{32}$$

is an implicational quantifier.

- If g is non-decreasing and h is non-increasing, then

$$Q_{g,h}(a, b) = g(a) \star h(b) \tag{33}$$

is an implicational quantifier.

Proof. (31) It follows from the monotonicity of \rightarrow in the second argument and the antitonicity in the second. If $a \leq a'$ and $b' \leq b$ then $g(a') \leq g(a)$ and $h(b) \leq h(b')$, and consequently

$$\begin{aligned} g(a) \rightarrow h(b) &\leq g(a') \rightarrow h(b), \\ g(a') \rightarrow h(b) &\leq g(a') \rightarrow h(b'). \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$g(a) \rightarrow h(b) \leq g(a') \rightarrow h(b'),$$

which shows that $Q_{g,h}(a, b) \leq Q_{g,h}(a', b')$, which means that $Q_{g,h}$ is an implicational quantifier.

(32) It follows directly from the fact that \rightarrow^{-1} is monotone in the first argument and antitone in the second, and non-decreasing functions do not affect these properties. \square

Remark 1. Let $g : \overline{\mathbb{R}}_0^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a non-decreasing function, $h : \overline{\mathbb{R}}_0^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a non-increasing function and $\underline{\vee}$ be an arbitrary t-conorm. Then

$$Q_{g,h}(a, b) = g(a) \underline{\vee} h(b) \tag{34}$$

is an implicational quantifier.

Convention 3. In the context where the functions g and h are identical, we simplify our notation in (31) and (32) by employing a single subscript. If the functions are too complex or if including subscripts would clutter the notation, we omit the subscripts altogether.

In fact, (29) and (30) are special cases of (32) as well as (31).

Example 3. Consider a probability P of fuzzy events that is a monotone mapping from fuzzy sets to the unit interval, i.e., if fuzzy sets A, B on X are such that $A \subseteq B$ then $P(A) \leq P(B)$.

- Moreover, let n be a number of rows in D . Hence, obviously

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{x/n}(a, b) &= b/n \rightarrow a/n = P(A \cap \bar{B}) \rightarrow P(A \cap B) \\ &= b_R \rightarrow a_R = Q_{I_d}(a_R, b_R), \end{aligned} \tag{35}$$

is an implicational quantifier.

Fig. 2. Input data.

- In the case of the product t-norm \star , we have that

$$P(B | A) = P_A(B) = \frac{a}{a + b} = \frac{a_R}{a_R + b_R} \tag{36}$$

and $P_A(B) \leq P_A(B')$ whenever $B \subseteq B'$. Consequently

$$g_A(x) = x/|A| = x/(a + b), \tag{37}$$

$$Q_{g_A}(a, b) = (b/(a + b)) \rightarrow (a/(a + b)) = P_A(\bar{B}) \rightarrow P_A(B). \tag{38}$$

Example 4. The following are examples of implicational quantifiers:

$$Q_1(a, b) = a/(a + b) = 1 \rightarrow (a/(a + b)), \tag{39}$$

$$Q_2(a, b) = (0.9^{a+1}) \rightarrow_L (0.6^{b+1}), \tag{40}$$

$$Q_3(a, b) = (0.8^{a+1}) \rightarrow_P (0.8^{b+1}), \tag{41}$$

$$Q_4(a, b) = (b/(a + b)) \rightarrow_L (a/(a + b)), \tag{42}$$

$$Q_5(a, b) = (b/(a + b)) \rightarrow_P (a/(a + b)), \tag{43}$$

for all a, b being positive reals, where \rightarrow_L is Łukasiewicz residuum and \rightarrow_P is the product residuum defined as

$$x \rightarrow_L y = \min(1, 1 - x + y), \tag{44}$$

$$x \rightarrow_P y = \min(1, y/x), \tag{45}$$

for all $x, y \in [0, 1]$.

Example 5.

- Consider fuzzy sets A from Fig. 3(a), B, C from Fig. 3(c), and input data D from Fig. 2. Suppose the data from Fig. 2 illustrates commodity sales over time. In this context, the fuzzy set A represents a time segment, while the fuzzy sets B and C represent commodity sales, all characterized by imprecise boundaries. The values $\{a, b\}$ of the four-fold table for A, B w.r.t. D are $\{a, b\} = \{2.76, 10.64\}$, and for A, C w.r.t. D , we obtain $\{a, b\} = \{0, 13.4\}$.

The values of quantifiers Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_5 defined by (39)–(43), respectively, are the following:

i	1	2	3	4	5
$Q_i(A, B)$	0.21	0.33	0.17	0.41	0.26
$Q_i(A, C)$	0.0	0.1	0.05	0.0	0.0

Fig. 3. Fuzzy sets A (Fig. 3(a) and (b)) related to Example 5, fuzzy sets C (blue line) and B (green line). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 4. Plots of functions from Example 6 with various parameter k .

- Consider fuzzy sets A from Fig. 3(b), B, C from Fig. 3(c), and input data D from Fig. 2. The values $\{a, b\}$ of the four-fold table for A, B w.r.t. D , we obtain $\{a, b\} = \{6.61, 6.79\}$, and for A, C w.r.t. D , we obtain $\{a, b\} = \{2.95, 10.45\}$. The values of quantifiers Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_5 defined by (39)–(43), respectively, are the following:

i	1	2	3	4	5
$Q_i(A, B)$	0.49	0.57	0.96	0.99	0.97
$Q_i(A, C)$	0.22	0.34	0.19	0.44	0.28

Example 6. We present several examples of non-increasing functions on the unit interval that can be used to construct implicational quantifiers by (31):

$$g_1(x) = 1 - (x/k)^2, k \geq 1 \tag{46}$$

$$g_2(x) = \max(0, (k - x)/k), k > 0 \tag{47}$$

$$g_3(x) = \exp(-x/k), k > 0 \tag{48}$$

$$g_4(x) = 1 - \sqrt{1 - (k - x)^2/k^2}, k \geq 1 \tag{49}$$

$$g_5(x) = \max(0, \ln(k - x + 1)/\ln(k + 1)), k > 0 \tag{50}$$

$$g_6(x) = \min\left(1, \frac{k - 1}{k \ln(k)} \cdot \ln\left(\frac{k - 1}{k^x - 1}\right)\right), k > 0 \text{ and } k \neq 1. \tag{51}$$

For visualisations see Fig. 4. Observe that g_6 is an additive generator of the Frank family of t-norms bounded by 1.

3.1.2. Simple quantifiers

A simple quantifier, characterized by its monotonic dependency on a single four-fold table argument a , can be defined using a non-decreasing mapping $g : \overline{\mathbb{R}}_0^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$ as follows:

$$Q(A, B) = q(a) = g(a). \tag{52}$$

Simple quantifiers can be regarded as special instances of the implicational quantifiers of the form (31), where $h(b) = 0$, i.e., $Q(a) = g(a) \rightarrow 0$. Dually, it can be obtained from (32) as follows: $Q(a) = 1 \rightarrow h(a)$ that is exactly (52). And also from (33) by taking h as the constant function 1.

Example 7. The following are simple quantifiers:

$$Q_1(a) = a/(a + b) = a/n, \tag{53}$$

$$Q_2(a) = (0.9^{a+1}) \rightarrow 0, \tag{54}$$

$$Q_3(a) = \neg(0.8^{a+1}), \tag{55}$$

$$Q_4(a) = a / \sum_{x \in M} A(x), \tag{56}$$

Example 8. The following are generators of simple quantifiers:

$$g_1(x) = (x/k)^2, k \geq 1 \tag{57}$$

$$g_2(x) = 1 - \max(0, (k - x)/k), k > 0 \tag{58}$$

$$g_3(x) = \neg_Y^c(\exp(-x/c)), c > 0, \neg_Y^c - \text{Yager negation}, \tag{59}$$

$$g_4(x) = \frac{\ln(1 + cx)}{\ln(1 + c)}, c \in]-1, \infty], \tag{60}$$

$$g_5(x) = \frac{2}{\pi} \arctan(x). \tag{61}$$

3.2. Double implicational and equivalence quantifiers

In [30], constructions (see Lemmas 26 and 27 in [30]) of double implicational and equivalence quantifiers can be found. Let us recall them for the case of t-norm \star and t-conorm \vee :

$$Q^D(a, b, c) = Q(a, b) \star Q(a, c), \tag{62}$$

$$Q^E(a, b, c, d) = Q'(a, b, c) \vee Q'(d, b, c), \tag{63}$$

where Q is an implicational quantifier and Q' is a double implicational quantifier. In [30], it was additionally shown that every implicational quantifier that satisfies the boundary condition $(Q(\infty, \infty) = Q(0, 0) = 1, Q(0, \infty) = 0)$ is isomorphic to fuzzy implication.

Obviously, taking different quantifiers in the above formulas will not harm the joint monotonicity.

Theorem 2. Let Q, Q' be implicational quantifiers and D, D' be double implicational quantifiers. Then, for an arbitrary four-fold table, the expressions

$$D(a, b, c) = Q(a, b) \star Q'(a, c), \tag{64}$$

$$E(a, b, c, d) = D(a, b, c) \vee D'(d, b, c), \tag{65}$$

define double implicational and equivalence quantifiers, respectively.

Proof. (64) follows directly from the definitions of implicational and double implicational quantifiers and the fact that \star is monotone (nondecreasing) in each argument.

(65) follows from the definitions of an equivalence and a double implication quantifier, and \vee being nondecreasing in each argument, we get that E is the equivalence quantifier. \square

Example 9. If Q is an implicational quantifier, then $Q(0, c)$ is also an implicational quantifier such that $Q(0, c) \leq Q(a, c)$ for an arbitrary $a \in \overline{\mathbb{R}}_0^+$. Analogously, $D(d, b, \infty)$ is a double implicational quantifier such that $D(a, b, \infty) \leq D(a, b, c)$ for arbitrary $a, b, c \in \overline{\mathbb{R}}_0^+$. Hence, the following are examples of double implicational and equivalence quantifiers:

$$D_0(a, b, c) = Q(a, b) \star Q(0, c), \tag{66}$$

$$E_1(a, b, c, d) = D(a, b, c) \vee D(d, b, \infty), \tag{67}$$

$$E_2(a, b, c, d) = D(a, \infty, c) \vee D(d, b, \infty), \tag{68}$$

where D_0 is double implicational and E_1, E_2 are equivalence quantifiers. Moreover, E_2 is composed of two implicational quantifiers.

3.2.1. Double implicational quantifiers

In the following, we provide other, but similar, constructions.

Theorem 3. Let $g, h, k : \overline{\mathbb{R}}_0^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$.

- If g, h, k are non-increasing, then for an arbitrary four-fold table, the expression

$$Q_{g,h,k}(a, b, c) = g(a) \rightarrow (h(b) \star k(c)) \tag{69}$$

defines a double implicational quantifier.

- If g, h, k are nondecreasing, then for an arbitrary four-fold table, the expression

$$Q_{g,h,k}(a, b, c) = (h(b) \star k(c)) \rightarrow g(a) \tag{70}$$

defines a double implicational quantifier.

- If g is non-decreasing, h, k are non-increasing, and \star_1, \star_2 are fuzzy conjunctions, then for an arbitrary four-fold table, the expression

$$Q_{g,h,k}(a, b, c) = g(a) \star_1 h(b) \star_2 k(c) \tag{71}$$

defines a double implicational quantifier.

Proof. (69) From the monotonicity of \rightarrow in the second argument and the monotonicity of \star , we have the resulting joined monotonicity of $Q_{g,h,k}$. In fact, if $a \leq a'$ and $b' \leq b$ then $Q_{g,h}(a, b) \leq Q_{g,h}(a', b')$, that is,

$$g(a) \rightarrow h(b) \leq g(a') \rightarrow h(b').$$

Additionally, if $c' \leq c$ then $k(c') \geq k(c)$ and consequently,

$$g(a) \rightarrow (h(b) \star k(c)) \leq g(a') \rightarrow (h(b') \star k(c')),$$

which shows that $Q_{g,h,k}$ is the double implicational quantifier.

(70) It follows directly from Theorem 1 and the fact that \star is monotone in both arguments.

(71) It follows directly from the fact that \star_1, \star_2 are monotone in both arguments. \square

Now, let us compare our construction with that provided in [30].

Theorem 4. Let D be a double implicational quantifier given by (64) and D_0 be given by (66).

Then there exist non-increasing functions $g, h, k : \overline{\mathbb{R}}_0^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $g(0) = h(0) = k(0) = 1$ and $g(\infty) = h(\infty) = k(\infty) = 0$ and moreover, for an arbitrary four-fold table

$$D_0(a, b, c) \leq Q_{g,h,k}(a, b, c) \leq Q_{g^2,h,k}(a, b, c), \tag{72}$$

where $Q_{g,h,k}$ is given by (69) and $g^2(x) = g(x) \star g(x)$ for all $x \in [0, 1]$.

Proof. Since D is composed of two implicational quantifiers, there exist functions g, h, k that satisfy the boundary conditions, D can be expressed using fuzzy implication and additionally

$$\begin{aligned} D_0(a, b, c) &= Q_{g,h}(a, b) \star Q_{h,k}(0, c) \\ &= (g(a) \rightarrow h(b)) \star (1 \rightarrow k(c)) \leq g(a) \rightarrow (h(b) \star h(c)) \\ &= Q_{g,h,k}(a, b, c) \leq (g(a) \star g(a)) \rightarrow (h(b) \star h(c)) = Q_{g^2,h,k}(a, b, c). \end{aligned} \tag{73}$$

\square

3.2.2. Equivalence quantifiers

For the equivalence quantifiers, we have the following construction.

Theorem 5. Let \star_i be a fuzzy conjunction, for each $i = 1, 2, 3$, and let $g, h, k, l : \overline{\mathbb{R}}_0^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$.

- If g, h, k, l are non-increasing, then for an arbitrary four-fold table, the expression

$$Q_{g,h,k,l}(a, b, c, d) = (g(a) \star_1 l(d)) \rightarrow (h(b) \star_2 k(c)) \tag{74}$$

defines an equivalence quantifier.

- If g, h, k, l are nondecreasing, then for an arbitrary four-fold table, the expression

$$Q_{g,h,k,l}(a, b, c, d) = (h(b) \star_1 k(c)) \rightarrow (g(a) \star_2 l(d)) \tag{75}$$

defines an equivalence quantifier.

- If g, l are non-decreasing and h, k are non-increasing, then for an arbitrary four-fold table, the expression

$$Q_{g,h,k,l}(a, b, c, d) = g(a) \star_1 h(b) \star_2 k(c) \star_3 l(d) \tag{76}$$

defines an equivalence quantifier.

Proof. (74) We start from the results of Theorem 3, if $a \leq a', b' \leq b, c' \leq c$ then $Q_{g,h,k}(a, b, c) \leq Q_{g,h,k}(a', b', c')$, that is,

$$g(a) \rightarrow (h(b) \star_2 k(c)) \leq g(a') \rightarrow (h(b') \star_2 k(c')).$$

Additionally, if $d \leq d'$ then $l(d) \geq l(d')$; consequently, by the antitonicity of \rightarrow in the first argument, we obtain

$$(g(a) \star_1 l(d)) \rightarrow (h(b) \star_2 k(c)) \leq (g(a') \star_1 l(d')) \rightarrow (h(b') \star_2 k(c')),$$

which shows that $Q_{g,h,k,l}$ is an equivalence quantifier.

(75) Analogously as in the previous case.

(76) $Q_{g,h,k}(a, b, c)$ given by (71) is a double implicational quantifier. Hence

$$Q_{g,h,k}(a, b, c) = g(a) \star_1 h(b) \star_2 k(c) \leq g(a') \star_1 h(b') \star_2 k(c') = Q_{g,h,k}(a', b', c'),$$

for if $a \leq a', b' \leq b, c' \leq c$. Additionally, if $d \leq d'$ then $l(d) \leq l(d')$ and hence

$$Q_{g,h,k}(a, b, c) \star_3 l(d) \leq Q_{g,h,k}(a', b', c') \star_3 l(d').$$

□

4. Implicational fuzzy rules with weights given by an implicational quantifier

Weighted fuzzy rules play a crucial role in fuzzy logic systems, enhancing the accuracy and reliability of their outputs [1,35,36]. By adjusting the weights associated with these rules, one can fine-tune the system’s behavior and control its sensitivity to varying input conditions. These adjustments can be applied at different levels: the antecedent level, the consequent level, or across the entire rule [2]. In this discussion, we will focus on the last of these.

If the dependency being modeled is well understood, fuzzy rules can often be defined directly without additional computational effort. For instance, in cases of monotonic dependencies, such as the one illustrated in Fig. 5, rule creation can be straightforward. However, such situations are relatively rare in practical applications.

In practice, developing a fuzzy rule base (including weighted fuzzy rules) often requires leveraging input data, prompting the creation of numerous methods over the past decades. One such approach is demonstrated in Fig. 6, where neighborhoods $S(x, p)$ and $S'(y, q)$ are constructed for each data point (p, q) using predefined similarity relations S and S' . These neighborhoods are combined with an implicational rule $S(x, p) \rightarrow S'(y, q)$, followed by taking the minimum over all data points $(p, q) \in D$. For the dataset depicted in Fig. 2, this process results in the implicational model shown in Fig. 6. Notably, as the volume of data increases, the degrees in the final implicational model vanish (go to zero). This drawback diminishes both the interpretability and simplicity of the resulting rule base.

It can be advantageous to modify our setting and, for example, limit the number of fuzzy rules or utilize fuzzy sets with predefined linguistic interpretations. Such adjustments may help maintain clarity and simplify the rule base for better interpretability. Additionally, incorporating a gradual switching mechanism allows for prioritizing rules that are strongly supported by the given observations. Therefore, we propose a new model that integrates flexible switches with the conditional statements indicating their relevance to the input data. This approach introduces a novel perspective on weighted fuzzy rules.

Notably, there are two primary interpretations of fuzzy IF-THEN rules. The first employs a fuzzy conjunction to combine the internal components of a rule and \vee to aggregate rules. Our focus, however, is on a model that uses a fuzzy implication \rightarrow within individual rules and \wedge to combine them. This structure, known as the implicational model, has been extended to the weighted implicational model, as discussed in [37]. In the following, we present a weighted implicational model implementing implicational quantifier values computed based on a data matrix. The definition and the property (78) below are taken from [38].

Definition 7. Let D be a data matrix of the form (7). Consider $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{F}(X)$ and $\mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{F}(Y)$ to be nonempty finite systems of fuzzy sets. Moreover, let q be an implicational quantifier. Then

$$\text{F-RULES}_q^D(x, y) = \bigwedge_{(A,B) \in \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{B}} (q(A, B) \rightarrow [A(x) \rightarrow B(y)]), \tag{77}$$

for all $x \in X, y \in Y$.

We call F-RULES_q^D the *weighted implicational model* w.r.t. q and D .

Remark 2. In the case where the input domain X is multidimensional, i.e., $X = X_1 \times \dots \times X_k$, fuzzy sets $A \in \mathcal{F}(X)$ are typically constructed as fuzzy Cartesian products of fuzzy sets defined on each individual dimension X_i . The evaluation $A(x)$ for $x = (x_1, \dots, x_k) \in X$

(a) Implicational rules.

(b) Fuzzy intervals on X.

(c) Fuzzy intervals on Y.

Fig. 5. An implicational model in Fig. 5(a) utilizing fuzzy sets depicted in Fig. 5(b) and (c) for monotonic dependency of the form $y = x^2$ together with the noisy data $\{x_j, x_j^2 + \text{RandBetween}(-x_j, x_j)\}_{j=1}^{65}$ (scatter plot).

is then computed using a suitable t-norm aggregation over the component memberships $A_i(x_j)$. The definition of the weighted implicational model remains valid in this setting, with the antecedent space \mathcal{A} appropriately adapted to reflect multidimensional structures.

As the implicational quantifier gauges the dependence between two predicates based on observed data, it functions as a “switch” for the rule within the graded implicational data model of the above form. Consider the following scenario: when $q(A, B) = 1$, the weighted fuzzy rule $q(A, B) \rightarrow (A(x) \rightarrow B(y))$ simplifies to the standard fuzzy rule $A(x) \rightarrow B(y)$. Conversely, if $q(A, B) = 0$, the weighted fuzzy rule is consistently evaluated as 1, indicating that there is no dependency between A and B in the data provided. Generally,

Fig. 6. Example of implicative model based on similarity and input data in Fig. 2.

we can assert that the more data we have supporting the dependency, the higher the weight of the fuzzy rule becomes, bringing us closer to the non-weighted fuzzy rule (see Fig. 7), as described in the subsequent theorem.

Theorem 6. Let D, D' be data matrices of the form (7). Consider $A \subseteq F(X)$ and $B \subseteq F(Y)$ to be nonempty finite systems of fuzzy sets. Furthermore, let q be an implicational quantifier and $a(a'), b(b')$ be the values of a four-fold table for (A, B) w.r.t. $D (D')$ given by (8) for all $(A, B) \in \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{B}$, and $F\text{-RULES}_q^{D(D')}$ be given by (77).

- If $a \leq a'$ and $b' \leq b$ for all $(A, B) \in \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{B}$ then

$$F\text{-RULES}_q^{D'} \subseteq F\text{-RULES}_q^D. \tag{78}$$

- If $D \subseteq D'$ and $b' = b$ for all $(A, B) \in \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{B}$ then

$$F\text{-RULES}_q^{D'} \subseteq F\text{-RULES}_q^D. \tag{79}$$

Proof. Due to the antitony of \rightarrow in the first argument. \square

One might be surprised that we use an implicational quantifier that involves $a = \sum_{(x,y) \in D} (Ax \star By)$ and $b = \sum_{(x,y) \in D} (Ax \star \neg By)$ from the four-fold table to assess the degree of a conditional statement $Ax \rightarrow By$. However, since we are focusing solely on the kernel of the antecedent, it can be shown that the values are equivalent in this restricted domain (see (84)). Moreover, the degree of equivalence of the Cartesian product of A and B and $A \rightarrow B$ is higher than the degree of x belonging to $A \cap A$, and it is independent from the variable y (see (82)). This equivalence together with other properties is formally stated below.

Proposition 2. Let \rightarrow be residuated with \star , let \equiv be defined as

$$x \equiv y = (x \rightarrow y) \star (y \rightarrow x), \tag{80}$$

and $x \star x$ be denoted by x^2 . Moreover, let D be a data matrix and define its sub-matrix as

$$K = \{(x, y) \in D \mid A(x) = 1\}.$$

The following is valid for arbitrary $A \in F(X), B \in F(Y)$:

$$\sum_{(x,y) \in D} (A \times B)(x, y) \leq \sum_{(x,y) \in D} (Ax \rightarrow By), \tag{81}$$

$$(A \cap A)(x) \leq (A \times B)(x, y) \equiv (Ax \rightarrow By), \tag{82}$$

$$\sum_{(x,y) \in D} (A \cap A)(x) \star (Ax \rightarrow By) \leq \sum_{(x,y) \in D} (A \times B)(x, y), \tag{83}$$

$$\sum_{(x,y) \in K} (A \times B)(x, y) = \sum_{(x,y) \in K} (Ax \rightarrow By). \tag{84}$$

Proof. (81) follows from $Ax \star Ax \star By \leq By$, by applying the residuation property, and finally, by summation. (82) follows from $Ax \star (Ax \rightarrow By) \leq By$. And by the monotonicity of \star , we have $(Ax)^2 \star (Ax \rightarrow By) \leq Ax \star By$. Hence

$$(Ax)^2 \leq (Ax \rightarrow By) \rightarrow (Ax \star By).$$

And adding the fact that $Ax \star By \leq Ax \rightarrow By$, we obtain the resulting inequality.

(83) it follows directly from (82). \square

Fig. 7. Examples of weighted fuzzy rules with different weights.

4.1. Algorithm for constructing weighted fuzzy rules

Below, we present an algorithm that outlines one of the possible processes of constructing and analyzing weighted fuzzy rules based on input data that represents observations on a function $f : X \rightarrow Y$, where the input domain X is composed of multiple dimensions X_1, \dots, X_k . The algorithm begins by discretizing each input variable and defining fuzzy sets over these discretized domains. Fuzzy sets on the output domain Y are then generated based on weighted means and variances, computed with respect to the fuzzy sets on X . Subsequently, the values of quantifiers are evaluated, and the model of the form (77) is constructed.

These steps ensure an accurate representation of the relationships within the data, allowing for the computation of membership values and confidence measures of the final model. The overall computational complexity of the method depends on the number of input variables k , the number of fuzzy sets per variable m , and the number of data points n . In the worst case, the number of antecedent combinations grows exponentially as $\mathcal{O}(m^k)$, leading to a total time complexity of approximately $\mathcal{O}(n \cdot m^k)$ for computing all rule supports and evaluating the quantifiers.

Despite this, optimizations such as pruning low-support combinations or using sparse data representations can significantly reduce the effective runtime in practice. Algorithm 1 describes the step-by-step procedure for implementing this method in the one-

dimensional case, including data discretization, fuzzy set construction, and rule evaluation with a preset quantifier. The extension to higher-dimensional input domains is straightforward.

Algorithm 1 Algorithm for quantifier-based fuzzy model.

```

1: Input: Data  $df$  with columns  $x$  and  $fx$ , parameters of slopes  $d_1, d_2$ , test data  $X, Y$ 
2: Initialize:  $nodes_x, nodes_yL, nodes_yR, quantifier, model$ 
3: Extract  $data_x, data_{valx}$  from  $df$ 
4: Compute  $min_x, max_x, min_{fx}, max_{fx}$  as range values of  $data_x$  and  $data_{valx}$ 
5: Discretize Input Domain:
6: Compute  $nodes_x$  as intervals between  $min_x$  and  $max_x$  with  $dx$  steps
7: Generate Fuzzy Intervals on  $x$ :
8: for  $i \in [0, len(nodes_x) - 1]$  do
9:   Compute fuzzy set  $A_i$  with the kernel  $[nodes_x[i], nodes_x[i + 1]]$  and the parameter of slope  $d_1$ 
10: end for
11: Compute Weighted Means and Variance:
12: for  $i \in [0, len(nodes_x) - 1]$  do
13:   Compute weighted mean and variance of  $data_{valx}$  w.r.t.  $A_i$ 
14:   Append  $weighted\_mean \pm variance$  to  $nodes_yL$  and  $nodes_yR$ 
15: end for
16: Generate Fuzzy Intervals on  $y$ :
17: for  $i \in [0, len(nodes_yL)]$  do
18:   Compute fuzzy set  $B_i$  with the kernel  $[nodes_yL[i], nodes_yR[i]]$  and the parameter of slope  $d_2$ 
19: end for
20: Compute Quantifiers:
21: for  $i \in [0, len(nodes_yL)]$  do
22:   Generate  $(a, b) = FourFoldTable(A_i, B_i)$ 
23:   Calculate the value of quantifier  $q = Q(a, b)$ 
24:   Append  $q$  to  $quantifier$ 
25: end for
26: Compute Membership Values of the Model for the Test Data:
27: for  $i \in [0, len(X)]$  do
28:   for  $k \in [0, len(nodes_yL)]$  do
29:     Compute  $m[k, i] = quantifier[k] \rightarrow (A_k(X[i]) \rightarrow B_k(Y[i]))$ 
30:     Append  $m[k, i]$  to  $m[k]$ 
31:   end for
32:   Compute  $model[i] = min(m[k]; \text{ for all } k)$ 
33: end for
34: Output:  $nodes_yL, nodes_yR, quantifiers, model$ 

```

The following example aims to clarify the selection of antecedents and consequents in weighted implicational rules of the form (77) using Algorithm 1, as well as the meaning and interpretation of the applied implicational quantifier by means of visual illustrations.

Example 10. Let us consider a data matrix as in Fig. 2, i.e., the noisy x^2 . Moreover, let the values of the four-fold table for each A_i, B_i be denoted by (a_i, b_i, c_i, d_i) , for all $i \in I$. Moreover, let the implicational quantifier Q be given by

$$Q(A_i, B_i) = q_i = 0.9^{(a_i+1)} \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} 0.6^{(b_i+1)}$$

where $\rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}}$ is Łukasiewicz implication. For a visualization of Q see Fig. 8 below.

1. The values of $\bar{q} = (q_1, \dots, q_{10})$ for the fuzzy sets $(A_i, B_i), i = 1, \dots, 5$, depicted in Fig. 9 are the following

$$\bar{q} = [0.97, 0.9, 0.85, 0.8, 0.75]$$

with the following boundaries of kernels for fuzzy sets B_i :

$$nodes_yL = [0.04, 1.45, 6.49, 15.86, 25.4],$$

$$nodes_yR = [2.05, 6.64, 16.31, 27.2, 38.49].$$

From Fig. 8, we observe that the values of Q decrease rapidly for small values of a_i , leading to lower quantifier values \bar{q} in this case.

2. The values of $\bar{q}' = (q_1, \dots, q_{10})$ for the fuzzy sets $(A_i, B_i), i = 1, \dots, 10$, depicted in Fig. 10 are the following

$$\bar{q}' = [0.98, 0.97, 0.94, 0.89, 0.89, 0.85, 0.86, 0.81, 0.78, 0.8]$$

Fig. 8. Quantifier Q from Example 10.

with the following boundaries of kernels for fuzzy sets B_i :

$$nodes_{y,L} = [0.01, 0.15, 1.08, 2.61, 5.04, 10.14, 14.64, 18.94, 24.59, 30.27],$$

$$nodes_{y,R} = [0.92, 2.2, 4.06, 7.67, 13.2, 17.4, 22.45, 29.18, 36.65, 41.15].$$

3. The values of $\vec{q}'' = (q_1, \dots, q_{10})$ for the fuzzy sets (A_i, B_i) , $i = 1, \dots, 10$, depicted in Fig. 11 are the following

$$\vec{q}'' = [0.95, 0.89, 0.84, 0.73, 0.57, 0.62, 0.61, 0.51, 0.46, 0.47]$$

with the following boundaries of kernels for fuzzy sets B_i :

$$nodes_{y,L} = [0.38, 0.97, 2.27, 4.64, 8.31, 13.04, 17.76, 23.04, 29.42, 34.62],$$

$$nodes_{y,R} = [0.56, 1.38, 2.86, 5.65, 9.94, 14.5, 19.33, 25.09, 31.83, 36.8].$$

The vector \vec{q}'' is smaller than \vec{q}' (in the sense of each component) since the consequent fuzzy sets $\{B_i\}_{i=1}^{10}$ in the third case are all subfunctions of the consequents used in the second case. In the third case depicted in Fig. 11, the kernels of the consequents do not cover all the data, and the situation worsens as the index increases. This is also reflected in the values of the quantifier, which decrease with the growing index. The value of the quantifier can be interpreted as the degree to which the vaguely formulated statement “all data are covered by the particular rule” holds.

Understanding the relationship between economic development and demographic indicators is a key task in data-driven social science. In this example, we use publicly available data from the World Bank to explore how a country’s gross domestic product (GDP) per capita relates to its total fertility rate—that is, the average number of births per woman. This simple but insightful analysis highlights how rules with quantifiers can help explain human behavior on a global scale.

Example 11 (World Bank data). Given a data set [39], we extract two specific indicators:

- **X:** GDP per capita (current US\$)—a common measure of a country’s economic output and standard of living.
- **Y:** Fertility rate, total (births per woman)—a demographic measure that often reflects social, economic, and health-related factors.

These two indicators are known to exhibit a nonlinear and potentially inverse relationship, with higher-income countries typically showing lower fertility rates.

We apply several regression models to capture this nonlinear relationship; see the top-left graph in Fig. 12:

Fig. 9. Weighted implicational fuzzy rules at the top from Example 10–Part 1, for the data depicted in Fig. 2 with the fuzzy sets A_1, \dots, A_5 displayed in the lower left and the fuzzy sets B_1, \dots, B_5 in the lower right.

Table 1
Prediction error of regression models and implicational model on test data.

Model	MAE	MSE
Polynomial Regression	1.362	2.527
Exponential Regression	0.881	1.485
Logarithmic Regression	0.945	1.517
Implicational Model (MOM, 5 rules)	1.415	1.705
Implicational Model (MOM, 40 rules)	1.248	1.563
Implicational Model (MOM, 500 rules)	1.161	1.474

- Polynomial regression (2nd degree),
- Exponential regression,
- Logarithmic regression.

In addition, by applying Algorithm 1 with varying numbers of fuzzy sets, we constructed several interpretable implicational models. Among them, the model with 5 rules and the implicational quantifier given by fuzzy confidence is displayed in the top-right panel of Fig. 12, where its outputs under various defuzzification methods are visualized. For evaluation purposes, we also generated models with 40 and 500 rules, all using the MOM defuzzification. The choice of 5 rules illustrates the high interpretability and compactness of the model, while the 500-rule version emphasizes its descriptive richness and approximation capability at the expense of interpretability. A direct comparison of the 5-rule (left) and 500-rule (right) models, both with MOM defuzzification, is presented in Fig. 13.

The fitted models were then evaluated on separate test data; see Table 1 for the performance metrics. The table compares the prediction error of several regression models and implicational fuzzy models. According to the mean squared error (MSE), the implicational fuzzy model with 500 rules performs best, slightly surpassing the exponential regression. The logarithmic regression and the implicational models with 40 and 5 rules follow, while the polynomial regression shows the highest MSE. Looking at the mean

Fig. 10. Weighted implicational fuzzy rules at the top from Example 10–Part 2, for the data depicted in Fig. 2 with the fuzzy sets A_1, \dots, A_{10} displayed in the lower left and the fuzzy sets B_1, \dots, B_{10} in the lower right.

absolute error (MAE), the exponential regression achieves the lowest value, with the logarithmic regression and the implicational model with 500 rules performing only slightly worse.

It is worth noting that the implicational fuzzy model internally computes weighted averages when aggregating rule consequents. This procedure is mathematically closely related to minimizing the squared error, since the squared loss is sensitive to deviations from the weighted mean. As a result, the model tends to align more strongly with MSE optimization than with MAE, which explains why its performance is most competitive in terms of MSE.

Although the implication-based model with a lower number of rules exhibits higher prediction error compared to purely numerical approaches, it offers distinct advantages. This model is constructed from only five fuzzy IF–THEN rules, making it remarkably compact and easy to interpret. Each rule captures not only a specific semantic pattern such as:

“If GDP per capita is low, then fertility is high”
 “If GDP per capita is high, then fertility is low”

In addition to offering interpretable rule-based predictions, the model also computes the weighted mean and weighted variance of the predicted output. These statistics are calculated with respect to the degrees of rule activation, thereby reflecting the uncertainty inherent in the fuzzy inference process. Moreover, it provides information on the confidence of the prediction, estimated based on the distribution of rule activations observed in the training data. This enriches the output by quantifying both central tendency and variability, supporting more informed decision-making. To enhance interpretability, we assign linguistic labels to the five antecedent fuzzy sets A_1 through A_5 , namely *small*, *lower medium*, *medium*, *upper medium*, and *big*, based on their support and peak locations. These labels reflect the approximate ranges of the input variable *GDP per capita* to which each rule applies.

The resulting rules in Table 2 can be interpreted as fuzzy implications, where the variance-reflected in the width of the kernel of the respective fuzzy set-expresses the uncertainty of the output within the scope of each rule. Moreover, the validity of each implication holds at least to the degree specified by the quantifier employed in the model. In our case, all degrees associated with the used quantifier are high; therefore, we can be reasonably confident in the reliability of the resulting rule base.

Such formulations still align with human reasoning and domain knowledge, offering insights that are easily communicated as well as mathematically precise. Unlike black-box regression curves, the rule-based model facilitates transparency and explainability, which is especially valuable in sensitive domains like development policy.

Fig. 11. Weighted implicational fuzzy rules at the top from Example 10–Part 3, for the data depicted in Fig. 2 with the fuzzy sets A_1, \dots, A_{10} displayed in the lower left and the fuzzy sets B_1, \dots, B_{10} in the lower right.

Table 2
Linguistic interpretation of the generated implicational fuzzy rules with quantifiers.

Nr.	Rule	Quantifier
R_1	If GDP per capita is <i>small</i> then fertility is in average 3.9 ± 1.72	0.79
R_2	If GDP per capita is <i>lower medium</i> then fertility is in average 2.18 ± 0.74	0.90
R_3	If GDP per capita is <i>medium</i> then fertility is in average 1.69 ± 0.24	0.96
R_4	If GDP per capita is <i>upper medium</i> then fertility is in average 1.54 ± 0.16	0.98
R_5	If GDP per capita is <i>big</i> then fertility is in average 1.5 ± 0.08	0.99

In summary, while the implicational model may be less precise in terms of error metrics, it excels in providing a concise and interpretable representation of the underlying relationship in the data.

4.2. Association rule mining based implicational models with quantifiers in classification

Another effective way to construct fuzzy IF–THEN rules and to perform modeling based on implicational semantics with quantifiers is through the use of association rule mining techniques and suitably chosen quantifiers. These approaches enable the systematic discovery of data-driven dependencies. In this section, we demonstrate that integrating fuzzy set theory with both simple and implicational GUHA quantifiers into the rule mining process enables the derivation of interpretable and semantically grounded rules, suitable for both descriptive and predictive modeling.

Let us outline the main steps of the procedure. Fuzzy association rules [40] are used to identify relationships between input variables based on fuzzified data, evaluated using various quality metrics, including selected GUHA quantifiers. We employ the `dig_associations()` function from the `nuggets` R package [10], which analyzes combinations of fuzzy sets of antecedents A and consequents B using both simple quantifiers (e.g., support $q_S(a) = a/n$) and implicational fuzzy quantifiers (e.g., $q_C(a, b) = \frac{a}{a+b}$), i.e., this function performs GUHA-procedure ASSOC with single succedent. Moreover, the function supports the evaluation of externally implemented quantifiers in conjunction with the mined rules.

Fig. 12. Weighted implicational fuzzy rules at the top for the World Bank data with the fuzzy sets A_1, \dots, A_5 displayed in the lower left and the fuzzy sets B_1, \dots, B_5 in the lower right.

Fig. 13. Models of weighted implicational fuzzy rules for the World Bank data, with five rules displayed on the left and 500 rules on the right, both defuzzified using MOM indicated by the red line. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

After rule generation, a superset-based filtering step is applied to remove redundant or nested rules within the same consequent group, as developed in [41]. This procedure is based on the identity

$$\bigwedge_{i \in I} (A_i \rightarrow B) = \left(\bigvee_{i \in I} A_i \right) \rightarrow B,$$

which holds for every implication \rightarrow residuated with a continuous t -norm and for any index set I .

In the fuzzy inference phase, new input data \bar{x} is evaluated against the filtered set of rules $\{A^{(i)}, B^{(i)}\}_{i=1}^n$ using the model F-RULES $_q^D(\bar{x}, y)$ defined in (77) (see also Remark 2). Finally, defuzzification is performed using a standard defuzzification method.

In the case of a crisp classification problem with a predefined collection of crisp classes $C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_k\}$, the consequents are defined as

$$B_C(y) = \chi(y = C), \quad C \in C, \tag{85}$$

where $\chi : C^2 \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ is the characteristic function of the identity relation. For a given input \bar{x} , the model F-RULES $_q^D(\bar{x}, y)$ is then computed according to (77) for each $y \in C$ using the corresponding crisp consequent B_C .

The final class prediction is obtained by selecting the class label(s) with the highest value of F-RULES $_q^D(\bar{x}, y)$. In the case of ties, multiple top candidates are retained, which preserves uncertainty in the prediction. This is particularly useful in soft decision systems and diagnostic applications where ambiguous or borderline cases should not be arbitrarily resolved.

Remark 3 (Relationships to GUHA procedures). Since we generate fuzzy rules with single-variable consequents, we adopt the IMPL procedure with implicational quantifiers. In our setting, a question is a pair (A, C) , where A is an antecedent formed as a conjunction of elementary predicates from a collection \mathcal{A} , and $C \in C$ is a single consequent; negations are not allowed. The resulting rules hold in the data-induced model with respect to the chosen quantifier (defined by (86) in the example below).

In this special case (single-consequent rules without negation), IMPL coincides with the ASSOC variant. Furthermore, our interpretation of the rules generated with implicational quantifiers is structurally consistent with, and exhibits properties analogous to, those produced by the IMPL procedure. Despite these considerations, we refer to our approach as *association rule mining*, as this term is more widely recognized in both the engineering and fuzzy logic communities.

Algorithm 2 Crisp classification via fuzzy implicational rules with quantifiers.

- 1: **Input:** Fuzzified dataset, input \bar{x} , class set C
 - 2: Generate fuzzy association rules $\{A^{(i)}, B^{(i)}\}_{i=1}^n$ using `dig_associations()`
 - 3: Evaluate quality using simple and implicational quantifiers (e.g., support, confidence, q_C, q_L)
 - 4: **Filter** rules within each consequent group using superset-based rule reduction
 - 5: **for** each test instance \bar{x} **do**
 - 6: **for** each class $C \in C$ **do**
 - 7: Define consequent $B_C(y) = \chi(y = C)$ ▷ See Eq. (85)
 - 8: Compute model value F-RULES $_q^D(\bar{x}, C)$ using (77)
 - 9: **end for**
 - 10: Determine $\hat{y} = \arg \max_{C \in C} \text{F-RULES}_q^D(\bar{x}, C)$
 - 11: **if** multiple maxima occur **then**
 - 12: retain all top classes
 - 13: **end if**
 - 14: **end for**
 - 15: **Output:** Predicted class label(s) for each \bar{x}
-

Since we provide an example for crisp classes below, we present the algorithm and complexity analysis for this case only. The generalization to fuzzy or multi-valued consequents is straightforward.

The proposed fuzzy rule-based crisp classification procedure summarized in Algorithm 2 consists of several stages with differing computational costs:

- *Fuzzification*: Transforms n data samples with m features into fuzzy representations. This step has linear complexity: $\mathcal{O}(n \cdot m)$.
- *Association rule mining*: The most computationally intensive part. In the worst case, the number of candidate itemsets grows exponentially with the number of fuzzy variables. The overall complexity is $\mathcal{O}(2^m \cdot n)$ (see [42]), though pruning strategies reduce this in practice [43]. This reflects the fact that all subsets of features (there are 2^m) must be evaluated across the dataset of size n .
- *Quantifier evaluation*: Evaluating multiple quality measures (e.g., support, confidence, q_C, q_L) for each of the r generated rules is done in $\mathcal{O}(r)$ time and is negligible compared to rule generation.
- *Superset-based rule filtering*: For each group of rules with the same consequent (typically g rules), subset comparisons require $\mathcal{O}(g^2)$. For k classes and $r \approx k \cdot g$ total rules, the filtering complexity becomes $\mathcal{O}(k \cdot g^2)$.
- *Fuzzy inference*: For each test input \bar{x} and each rule, antecedent activation and quantifier aggregation are computed. With r rules and m features, the complexity is $\mathcal{O}(r \cdot m)$ per instance, i.e., $\mathcal{O}(t \cdot r \cdot m)$ for t test instances.
- *Defuzzification*: Selecting the class with the highest degree among k candidates has complexity $\mathcal{O}(k)$ per instance, or $\mathcal{O}(t \cdot k)$ in total.

The overall complexity is dominated by the exponential term in the rule mining step, $\mathcal{O}(2^m \cdot n)$, and the linear inference phase, $\mathcal{O}(t \cdot r \cdot m)$. Optimizing rule generation and filtering is thus crucial for scalability.

The following example demonstrates the use of quantified implicational fuzzy rules for crisp classification on the well-known iris dataset. The procedure is implemented in R and is available in the accompanying repository [44].

Example 12 (Classification of Iris Data). Let us consider the well-known Iris dataset, a standard benchmark commonly used for evaluating classification algorithms.

The main steps of the experiment are as follows:

Fig. 14. Fuzzy sets used for linguistic values: Small, Medium, and Big.

Table 3
Top 5 fuzzy association rules sorted by confidence.

Antecedents	Consequent	Conf.	Supp.
{me.Sepal.Length, sm.Petal.Width, sm.Sepal.Width}	{Species = versicolor}	1.000	0.017
{me.Sepal.Length, sm.Petal.Width, sm.Sepal.Width}	{Species = versicolor}	1.000	0.017
{sm.Petal.Length}	{Species = setosa}	0.967	0.333
{sm.Petal.Length}	{Species = setosa}	0.967	0.333
{sm.Petal.Width}	{Species = setosa}	0.926	0.333

- The dataset is split into training and testing parts using a fixed set of indices for reproducibility.
- All data are fuzzified using linguistic terms, as shown in Fig. 14.
- We follow Algorithm 2 with thresholding based on support (0.01) and confidence measures (0.7). Moreover, the aggregation of the antecedents is performed via the min t -norm, and the model uses Łukasiewicz implication to aggregate quantifiers q_p (defined by (86)), antecedents, and consequents.
- The classification is performed on the unseen test data. Predictions are evaluated against the true labels using accuracy and class-wise metrics. Additionally, a heatmap visualization of the confusion matrix is presented.

In total, 424 fuzzy association rules were initially generated by the algorithm. After applying the superset-based filtering procedure to remove redundant and nested rules, 22 rules remained for inference and evaluation. The top five filtered fuzzy association rules, sorted by confidence, are presented in Table 3. Each rule includes its antecedent and consequent, along with the corresponding confidence and support values. The confidence indicates the reliability of the rule when the antecedent holds, while the support reflects how frequently the rule occurs in the dataset. The linguistic prefixes used in the rule antecedents follow a consistent naming convention: *sm.* denotes “small” (e.g., *sm.Sepal.Length* = small sepal length), *me.* denotes “medium”, and *bi.* denotes “big”. These linguistic terms correspond to the fuzzy sets obtained from fuzzification of the input features, see Fig. 14.

Notably, the first two rules in Table 3 achieve perfect confidence, though their support is relatively low, suggesting they are highly accurate but apply to a small subset of the data. Conversely, the remaining rules demonstrate slightly lower confidence but significantly higher support, indicating broader coverage with minor trade-offs in precision. Both parameters are used to define an *implicational quantifier* by combining them through the ordinary product. Specifically, the associated quantifier value q_p is defined as:

$$q_p(a, b) = q_S(a) \cdot q_C(a, b). \tag{86}$$

This product-based implicational quantifier retains the probabilistic semantics of support while incorporating the directional certainty given by confidence. It serves as a weighting mechanism in the implicational model, influencing the contribution of each rule during inference.

We compare the proposed method with the classical *A priori* algorithm implemented in the *arules* package [45,46], using the same support and confidence thresholds as in the previous experiment. Discretized numeric features are used to generate traditional association rules predicting the *Species* label. The best-matching rule per instance (with the highest confidence) is selected for prediction. The confusion matrix of this baseline method is also visualized to highlight differences in classification behavior and coverage.

Fig. 15. Confusion matrix heatmaps for the Weighted Implicational Model (left) and the Apriori algorithm (right).

Table 4
Confusion matrix metrics per class: Weighted Implicational (WI) Model vs. Apriori.

Metric	Averaging	WI Model	Apriori (arules)
Accuracy	Multiclass	1	0.967
Specificity	Macro	1	0.987
Positive Predictive Value	Macro	1	0.944
Negative Predictive Value	Macro	1	0.979
Precision	Macro	1	0.944
Recall	Macro	1	0.978
F-measure	Macro	1	0.958

Table 5
Cross-validation summary (mean ± sd) for 5- and 10-fold CV.

Folds	Model	Metric	Mean ± SD
5	Apriori	accuracy	0.9533 ± 0.0380
5	Apriori	F-measure	0.9531 ± 0.0383
5	Implicational	accuracy	0.9600 ± 0.0435
5	Implicational	F-measure	0.9598 ± 0.0436
10	Apriori	accuracy	0.9600 ± 0.0466
10	Apriori	F-measure	0.9592 ± 0.0480
10	Implicational	accuracy	0.9600 ± 0.0466
10	Implicational	F-measure	0.9597 ± 0.0468

Table 4 and Fig. 15 present a comparison of classification performance between the proposed Weighted Implicational fuzzy rule-based (WI) model and the classical Apriori algorithm implemented in the arules package. The standard metrics shown are derived from the confusion matrix, aggregated across all classes using both macro-averaging and multiclass formulations.

Remarkably, in this particular case, the WI model achieves perfect scores across all listed metrics. Thus, the model makes no classification errors on the given test set-it correctly identifies all true positives and negatives, and all predicted labels perfectly match the ground truth.

While the Apriori model also performs very well, achieving an accuracy of 0.967 along with high precision and recall, it still falls slightly behind the WI model. The difference is particularly notable in precision and recall (0.944 and 0.978 for Apriori, compared to 1.000 in both for the WI model), resulting in a lower F-measure (0.958 vs. 1.000).

These experimental results suggest that the WI model not only offers a semantically rich, interpretable framework based on quantified implications, but can also outperform traditional rule-based learners on structured data such as iris. We nevertheless caution that the near-perfect scores obtained on a single split may reflect overfitting to a particular partition or an overly expressive rule set. Therefore, we performed stratified 5- and 10-fold cross-validation to obtain robust out-of-sample estimates. As summarized in Table 5, the WI model matches or slightly exceeds the Apriori baseline (accuracy and F-measure ≈ 0.96 with comparable standard deviations), indicating that its advantage is not an artifact of a single split. Note that in the illustrative example above the linguistic context was defined by simple min-max bounds with midpoints, whereas in the cross-validation runs we used discretization breakpoints inferred by arules to construct the context.

5. Conclusions

We showed new constructions of a subclass of implicational quantifiers using fuzzy implications and conjunctions (see [Section 3](#), [Theorems 1, 3](#), and [5](#)). This method is grounded in the framework of standard fuzzy logic (with truth values from the unit interval $[0, 1]$) and is based on a construction originally introduced in [\[29\]](#). Additionally, we proposed a well-suited fuzzy relational model (see [Definition 7](#)) that utilizes implicational quantifiers as weights. We have provided a justification for this model (see [Theorem 6](#)) to establish a new well-founded class of weighted fuzzy rules that precisely aligns with intuitive expectations for their behavior.

To operationalize the approach, we formulated the complete algorithm for computing weighted fuzzy rules based on implicational quantifiers (see [Algorithm 1](#)), and we made its implementation publicly available. Furthermore, we demonstrated its application in classification tasks using fuzzy association rule mining ([Section 4.2](#)). The corresponding crisp classification procedure is formalized in [Algorithm 2](#), and its implementation-along with illustrative examples-is provided in a dedicated GitLab repository.

An investigation of the potential for further refinement and application of weighted fuzzy rules appears particularly promising, especially in light of their explainability, as illustrated in the presented examples (see [Examples 11](#) and [12](#)). These examples demonstrate how the interpretability of the weighted rules contributes to transparent decision-making, even in cases involving overlapping or ambiguous inputs. Overall, the implicational approach is competitive-and, under squared-loss criteria, advantageous-relative to classical regressions (see [Table 1](#), [Example 11](#)); moreover, stratified 5- and 10-fold cross-validation ([Table 5](#)) indicates that, on *iris* ([Example 12](#)), the WI model matches or slightly outperforms the strong Apriori baseline.

Our results indicate that weighted fuzzy rules offer a versatile mechanism for prioritizing and balancing conflicting or uncertain information, a common challenge in real-world scenarios. Their ability to incorporate nuanced degrees of relevance or reliability makes them particularly suitable for applications where inputs may be imprecise, incomplete, or derived from heterogeneous sources. By fine-tuning the weighting mechanisms and combining them with complementary methods, as in [Section 4.2](#), it becomes possible to deploy weighted fuzzy rules across a wide range of domains. This approach enhances decision-making in systems that must process multifaceted or conflicting inputs, such as in sensor fusion or diagnostic applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Martina Daňková: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization; **Dana Hliněná:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis.

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- Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process: During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT (OpenAI, GPT-5 model) solely for language editing and clarity improvement. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Data availability

I have shared links to my repositories in the manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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